

Optimizing Power Quality and System Stability in Grid-Connected Renewable Energy and BESS for Industrial and Commercial Loads

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KEYWORDS

Grid-connected renewable energy, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), power quality, system stability, Conservative Power Theory (CPT), harmonic distortion, voltage regulation, frequency stability, LCL filter, oscillating power compensation.

ABSTRACT

The integration of grid-connected renewable energy sources and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) in industrial and commercial applications presents challenges in maintaining power quality and system stability. The presence of linear, non-linear, and unbalanced loads, along with three-phase induction motors, leads to voltage fluctuations, harmonic distortion, and power imbalances. Additionally, the intermittent nature of solar energy further complicates system stability. This paper proposes an adaptive control strategy for multifunctional grid-tied inverters to mitigate power quality disturbances and optimize energy management between renewable sources, BESS, and the grid. Based on Conservative Power Theory (CPT), the strategy enables real-time extraction and compensation of oscillating power terms in the abc frame. A three-phase grid-tied inverter with an LCL filter is used in a laboratory-scale prototype to evaluate the system's effectiveness under various load conditions. Simulation results confirm that the proposed strategy reduces total harmonic distortion (THD), improves voltage regulation, and enhances frequency stability. Additionally, it ensures stable induction motor operation with constant torque and improves overall power quality in industrial and commercial settings. These findings validate the practical applicability of the proposed method for enhancing the performance and reliability of grid-connected renewable energy systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into industrial and commercial grid-connected power systems has gained significant momentum in recent years due to the increasing demand for clean energy and sustainability. However, the intermittent nature of solar photovoltaic (PV) introduces challenges related to power quality (PQ), voltage stability, and frequency regulation [1], [2]. These challenges are particularly evident in industrial and commercial facilities, where the presence of linear and nonlinear loads, three-phase induction motors (IMs), and unbalanced power demand results in significant harmonic distortions, oscillatory torques, and voltage imbalances [3], [4]. Addressing these issues is crucial to ensuring the reliability and efficiency of grid-connected hybrid renewable energy systems. To mitigate the impact of power oscillations, harmonic distortions, and reactive power imbalances, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and grid-tied inverters are widely deployed as part of power compensation strategies [5], [6]. Traditional approaches, such as passive filters and conventional PI-based controllers, have demonstrated limitations in dynamic industrial environments where load fluctuations and RES intermittency require fast and adaptive compensation mechanisms [7], [8]. In this context, active power filtering techniques and advanced control strategies, such as those based on the Conservative Power Theory (CPT), have emerged as effective solutions for real-time power quality enhancement [9]. By enabling instantaneous compensation of oscillatory power terms in the abc reference frame, CPT-based strategies enhance the ability of multifunctional grid-tied inverters (MFGTI) to regulate voltage, improve power factor, and suppress harmonic distortions [10]. This paper introduces a novel approach for integrating MFGTI with capacitor banks to enhance power quality in industrial and commercial power systems. The proposed system enables simultaneous active power injection, power factor compensation, and suppression of pulsating torques in three-phase induction motors, addressing key challenges associated with the intermittency of renewable energy sources and the presence of unbalanced industrial loads [11], [12]. By leveraging the firmware-based adaptive control of MFGTI, the system can dynamically respond to changing load conditions without requiring additional hardware modifications, making it a

cost-effective and scalable solution for modern industrial microgrids. The proposed system is validated through simulation studies conducted and demonstrating significant improvements in voltage regulation, harmonic mitigation, and overall power quality enhancement. The results confirm that the integration of MFGTI with capacitor banks not only reduces total harmonic distortion (THD) and voltage fluctuations but also prolongs the lifespan of induction motors by eliminating pulsating torques caused by power oscillations. Additionally, the multifunctionality of the inverter enables seamless compensation of residual reactive power, ensuring efficient energy utilization in industrial and commercial environments [13].

2. PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system integrates multifunctional grid-tied inverters (MFGTI) with capacitor banks in an industrial and commercial grid-connected renewable energy system. The primary objective is to enhance power quality, mitigate harmonic distortions, and ensure voltage stability while supporting three-phase induction motor (IM) loads. The system is designed to dynamically respond to fluctuations in renewable energy generation and industrial load variations without requiring additional hardware modifications. The system architecture consists of several key components, including renewable energy sources (RES), a multifunctional grid-tied inverter, a battery energy storage system (BESS), and capacitor banks. The RES, comprising solar photovoltaic (PV) system is connected to the grid through power electronic converters to facilitate efficient energy transfer. The MFGTI, equipped with an LCL filter, not only injects active power into the grid but also performs reactive power compensation and harmonic mitigation. Additionally, a lithium-ion BESS is integrated to stabilize power fluctuations and provide backup support during peak load conditions. Capacitor banks are strategically placed within the system to improve the overall power factor and reduce reactive power demand, thereby optimizing energy utilization and minimizing losses. The proposed system ensures seamless operation by dynamically adjusting power flow and compensating for grid disturbances, making it a reliable and efficient solution for industrial and commercial applications.

FIGURE 1. Interconnection of MFGTI to an industrial grid

3. MODELING AND DESIGNING OF PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The modeling and design of the proposed system configuration involve integrating renewable energy sources, power electronic converters, multifunctional grid-tied inverters (MFGTI), and energy storage elements to ensure enhanced power quality and grid stability in industrial and commercial environments. The system consists of photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy sources, which generate DC power and are interfaced with the grid through power electronic converters, including maximum power point tracking (MPPT)-enabled boost converters and voltage source inverters (VSI). The MPPT controllers ensure optimal energy harvesting from the renewable sources, while the VSI converts the regulated DC voltage into AC for seamless grid integration. A three-phase LCL-filtered MFGTI plays a crucial role in maintaining power quality by mitigating harmonics, compensating for reactive power, and stabilizing voltage fluctuations. The inverter operates under a Conservative Power Theory (CPT)-based control strategy, which enables real-time extraction of oscillatory power components and ensures effective compensation. Additionally, a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) is incorporated to balance power supply and demand, mitigating the intermittency of

renewable generation. The BESS is interfaced using a bidirectional DC-DC converter, allowing dynamic power exchange between the battery and the grid. Capacitor banks are included in the design to support reactive power compensation, improving the power factor and reducing strain on the grid. The control framework for the entire system is developed using a three-phase synchronous reference frame (SRF) for voltage and current regulation, enabling precise compensation for voltage imbalances and current harmonics. Furthermore, a phase-locked loop (PLL) ensures proper synchronization with the grid under varying load conditions.

A. Solar PV power generation system

The proposed grid-connected renewable energy setup includes a Solar Photovoltaic (PV) power generation system, which maximizes energy harvesting under varying solar irradiance and temperature conditions. The system uses a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) boost converter to regulate DC power extraction, enhancing overall system performance. The output is fed into a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI), which converts regulated DC voltage into AC for grid integration. The inverter operates with a high-frequency Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) technique to minimize switching losses and high power conversion efficiency.

An LCL filter is incorporated to reduce total harmonic distortion (THD) and comply with grid standards. The solar PV system is integrated with a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) through a bidirectional DC-DC converter to balance supply and demand. The power flow between the PV system, battery, and grid is managed through a coordinated energy management strategy.

a. Solar PV boost converter system configuration

The solar power system in a DC microgrid is crucial for efficient energy conversion and integration with other renewable energy sources. A perturb and observe (P&O) maximum power point tracking (MPPT) boost converter is used to optimize power extraction from the photovoltaic (PV) array, ensuring it operates at its maximum power point under varying solar irradiance conditions. The P&O MPPT algorithm continuously adjusts the operating point by introducing small perturbations to the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter. This architecture ensures stable power distribution for EV fast charging stations, minimizing power losses and improving overall efficiency. The DC microgrid benefits from this configuration by achieving improved renewable energy utilization, reduced reliance on grid power, and enhanced power quality. The bidirectional energy flow capability allows for effective integration with battery storage systems, ensuring energy availability even during low solar generation periods. Implementing this solar P&O MPPT boost converter allows the DC microgrid to manage power distribution, support multiple EV chargers, and enhance sustainability by reducing carbon emissions through increased renewable energy penetration.

Fig. 2 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

1. Single-Diode Solar PV Model: Designing a single-diode solar PV model involves analyzing the electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic (PV) cell.

The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used to simulate the behavior of a PV cell. This model includes one diode, a current source, and series and shunt resistances to represent losses as shown in fig.5.

2. Basic Equation of the Single-Diode Model: The equation that governs the behavior of the single-diode PV model is derived from Kirchhoff's current law (KCL):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_{sh} \tag{1}$$

Where: I = output current of the PV module (A), I_{ph} = photocurrent, the current generated by light (A), I_D = diode current (A), I_{sh} = shunt current (A)

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar.

3. Diode Current (I_D): The current through the diode is described by the Shockley diode equation:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) \tag{2}$$

Where: I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode (A), V = voltage across the PV cell (V), R_s = series resistance (Ω), n = diode ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2), V_t = thermal voltage (V), given by $V_t = qkT$

Here:

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K), T = temperature in Kelvin (K), q = electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)

4. Shunt Current (I_{sh}): The current through the shunt resistance R_{sh} is modeled as:

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \tag{3}$$

5. Equation of the Single-Diode PV Model: By substituting the expressions for I_D and I_{sh} into the main current equation, we get the complete form of the single-diode model:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \tag{4}$$

6. Photocurrent I_{ph} : The current generated by the cell due to light is proportional to the incident light and is affected by temperature. It can be modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{ph,ref} + \mu I_{ph} \cdot (T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

Where: $I_{ph,ref}$ = reference photocurrent at standard test conditions (STC), I_{ph} = temperature coefficient of photocurrent (A/°C), T = cell temperature (°C), T_{ref} = reference temperature (usually 25°C), G = irradiance (W/m²), G_{ref} = reference irradiance at STC (1000 W/m²)

7. Saturation Current I_0 : The reverse saturation current varies exponentially with temperature:

$$I_0 = I_{0,ref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}}\right)^3 e^{\frac{E_g}{nV_t} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T}\right)} \quad (6)$$

Where: $I_{0,ref}$ = reverse saturation current at reference temperature, E_g = bandgap energy of the semiconductor (typically 1.1 eV for silicon)

b. P&O MPPT Algorithm

The P&O MPPT algorithm adjusts the duty cycle (D) of the boost converter based on small perturbations to the PV voltage. The power change is determined as follows:

4. flow chart of P&O MPPT algorithm

$$\Delta P = P(k) - P(k - 1) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta V = V(k) - V(k - 1) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P > 0 \text{ and } \Delta V > 0, \text{ increase } V_{pv} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P < 0 \text{ and } \Delta V > 0, \text{ decrease } V_{pv} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P > 0 \text{ and } \Delta V < 0, \text{ decrease } V_{pv} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P < 0 \text{ and } \Delta V < 0, \text{ increase } V_{pv} \quad (12)$$

The updated duty cycle is calculated as:

$$D(k + 1) = D(k) + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta P) \quad (13)$$

Where α is the step size for duty cycle adjustment.

c. Bidirectional Buck-Boost Converter for EV Charging in DC Microgrid

The bidirectional buck-boost converter plays a crucial role in managing energy flow between the battery

energy storage system (BESS) and the DC bus in a microgrid. This converter enables both charging and discharging of the battery, ensuring stable power delivery for electric vehicle (EV) charging. In buck mode, the converter steps down the DC bus voltage to charge the battery, while in boost mode, it steps up the battery voltage to supply power to the microgrid or EV load. The control strategy dynamically adjusts the duty cycle to regulate power flow efficiently. The converter also helps stabilize the DC bus voltage, mitigating fluctuations from intermittent renewable energy sources like solar and wind. The energy management strategy ensures optimal charging and discharging cycles, enhancing battery lifespan and overall system efficiency.

1. Buck Mode (Battery Charging)

Output Voltage in Buck Mode:

$$V_b = D \cdot V_{dc} \quad (14)$$

Where: V_b = Battery voltage, V_{dc} = DC bus voltage, D = Duty cycle ($0 < D < 1$)

Inductor Current Ripple in Buck Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{(1-D)V_{dc}}{L f_s} \quad (15)$$

Where: ΔI_L = Inductor current ripple, L = Inductor value, f_s = Switching frequency

2. Boost Mode (Battery Discharging)

Output Voltage in Boost Mode:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_b}{1-D} \quad (16)$$

Inductor Current Ripple in Boost Mode:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_b}{1-D} \quad (17)$$

Fig.5

principle operation bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter

d. Double-Loop Controller for EV Charging System

The control strategy for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves a double-loop control system to ensure efficient, stable, and safe charging. The outer voltage loop maintains a constant DC bus voltage, while the inner

current loop regulates the battery charging current. A Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is used in both loops to minimize steady-state error and improve dynamic performance.

Fig. 6 double loop ev charging controller

1. Outer Voltage Loop: DC Bus Voltage Control

The outer voltage loop ensures the DC bus voltage (V_{dc}) remains stable and within the desired range. Since variations in EV charging loads and grid fluctuations affect the DC bus voltage, this loop provides a reference current (I_{ev}^*) for the inner current loop.

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_v(t) = V_{dc}^* - V_{dc} \quad (18)$$

PI Controller Output (Reference EV Charging Current (I_{ev}^*))

$$I_{ev}^*(t) = K_{pv}e_v(t) + k_{iv}\int e_v(t) dt \quad (19)$$

Where: I_{ev}^* = Reference charging current for the inner loop, K_{pv} = Proportional gain of voltage controller, K_{iv} = Integral gain of voltage controller

This reference current is then passed to the inner current loop for precise battery charging control.

2. Inner Current Loop: Battery Current Control

The inner current loop ensures the EV battery is charged with a smooth and regulated current to prevent over current issues and battery degradation. The PI controller in this loop generates the duty cycle for the DC-DC converter (buck or boost).

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_i(t) = I_{ev}^* - I_{ev} \quad (20)$$

PI Controller Output (Duty Cycle Control)

$$D(t) = K_{pi}e_i(t) + k_{ii}\int e_i(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Where: D = Duty cycle of the DC-DC converter, K_{pi} = Proportional gain of current controller, K_{ii} = Integral gain of current controller

This duty cycle (D) is applied to the DC-DC converter, adjusting the output voltage and current to regulate battery charging.

B. Designing for Grid Connected AC-DC MFGTI Controller

The Power Electronics Converter (PEC) control algorithm is implemented in natural coordinates (abc). A simplified control system diagram is presented in Fig. 7, showing the generation of reference signals from the Conservative Power Theory (CPT) and the control loops used. The modeling and design of the controllers are based on [14], [15], and [16].

The proposed control system utilizes two loops:

1. Inner Loop: Controls the output current of the Multi-Functional Grid-Tied Inverter (MFGTI), denoted as iMFGTI.
2. Outer Loop: Maintains a constant voltage at the DC bus, denoted as vCC.

Since the system in Fig. 1 is a three-phase system with three wires, the phase c current is obtained by summing the currents of the MFGTI:

Current Controller Design

The controller for the MFGTI's output current is based on a multi-resonant proportional controller [17], given by:

$$G_s(s) = K_c + \sum_{h=1,3,5} \frac{2K_{IPR}\omega_{CPRS}}{s^2 + 2\omega_{CPRS} + (h\omega_0)^2} \quad (22)$$

where: h = harmonic order, ω_0 = fundamental frequency of the grid, K_c = proportional gain, K_{IPR} = integral gain, ω_{CPR} = bandwidth of the resonant controller

The proportional gain K_c is calculated to ensure a certain cross-over frequency ω_c of the uncompensated open-loop transfer function $OLTF_{nc}(s)$ as discussed in [18]:

$$K_c = \frac{1}{|OLTF_{nc}(\omega_c)|} \quad (23)$$

a. DC Bus Voltage Regulation

A Proportional-Integral (PI) Controller is used for regulating the DC bus voltage, designed according to [14]. The PI regulator is designed with a sufficiently narrow bandwidth to avoid oscillations in the peak value of the current reference and minimize interaction with the current controller [18]:

$$P_{IDC}(s) = K_{PDC} + \frac{K_{IDC}}{s} \quad (24)$$

where:

- K_{PDC} = proportional gain of the DC voltage controller
- K_{IDC} = integral gain of the DC voltage controller

b. System Specifications

The MFGTI was designed with a switching frequency of 18 kHz due to the single update modulation strategy and the physical design of the magnetic devices.

The control parameters are as follows (from Table 3):

- Current loop bandwidth: 1.2 kHz (to compensate current harmonics with a phase margin of 45°).

- DC voltage PI compensator bandwidth: 7 Hz (to ensure system stability with a phase margin of 70°).

DC bus voltage regulation: Maintains a steady 700 V output.

FIGURE 7. Control system and reference signals generation for proposed MFGTI.

c. OSCILLATORY POWER COMPONENTS

The decomposition of instantaneous power considered in this paper is based on average and oscillatory components, taking the CPT as a framework for such a task [19]. The CPT, which is an approach defined in the time domain, is applicable to any periodic signal, enabling the analysis of both single-phase and multi-phase electrical systems. The CPT decomposes current and power signals into orthogonal components, yielding physically meaningful quantities without the need for PLL or coordinate transformations. Due to the decoupling between the obtained current components, the CPT has proven to be an effective tool for generating reference signals to compensate disturbances in APF [20], MFGTI [21], [22], [23], [15] and microgrids [24], [25], [26]. A few applications can be found in [27]. The CPT defines two conservative quantities known as instantaneous power, $p(t)$, and instantaneous reactive energy, [19]. The former is given by the dot product of voltage and current vectors, as shown in Equation (25).

On the other hand, utilizes the vector of the unbiased time integral of voltages (\hat{v}_m) and the vector of current, as shown in Equation (26). Further details regarding the CPT and its main quantities are discussed in [45].

The definition of is presented in Equation (27), in which represents the phases and , respectively:

$$p(t) = [v_a \ v_b \ v_c] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

$$p(t) = [\hat{v}_a \ \hat{v}_b \ \hat{v}_c] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$\hat{v}_m = \int_0^t v_m(\tau) d\tau - \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t v_m(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \quad (27)$$

Observe that the second term in Equation (27) represents the average value of the voltage over a period . Moving Average Filters (MAF) are employed to calculate the average values of and as shown in Equations (28) and (29), respectively, yielding the active power and the reactive energy :

$$\bar{\omega}(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \omega(t) dt = W \quad (28)$$

$$\bar{p}(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T p(t) dt = P \quad (29)$$

Similarly to the theory [28], the terms and defined in Equations (25) and (26) can be decomposed into average and oscillatory components, as shown in Equations (30) and (31), respectively. In the notation used, represents the oscillating components of each term, while indicates the average components:

$$\omega(t) = \bar{\omega} + \tilde{\omega} \quad (30)$$

$$p(t) = \bar{p} + \tilde{p} \quad (31)$$

Note that the average and oscillatory components are valid regardless of the voltage and current waveforms. This characteristic makes the application of this methodology valid for both sinusoidal and non-sinusoidal voltage conditions.

d. REFERENCE SIGNALS FOR APF FUNCTION TO POWER QUALITY IMPROVEMENT

With the instantaneous power and reactive energy terms defined in Equations (9) and (10), two instantaneous current components can be defined, namely instantaneous active (i_p) and reactive (i_w) currents:

$$i_w(t) = \bar{i}_\omega + \tilde{i}_\omega = \frac{\bar{w}}{\hat{v}_{abc}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_a \\ \hat{v}_b \\ \hat{v}_c \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\tilde{w}}{\hat{v}_{abc}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_a \\ \hat{v}_b \\ \hat{v}_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

$$i_p(t) = \bar{i}_p + \tilde{i}_p = \frac{\bar{p}}{v_{abc}^2} \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\tilde{p}}{v_{abc}^2} \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

Where $v_{abc}^2 = v_a^2 + v_b^2 + v_c^2$ and $\hat{v}_{abc}^2 = \hat{v}_a^2 + \hat{v}_b^2 + \hat{v}_c^2$ are the instantaneous collective values of voltages and their unbiased time integral values, Since the oscillatory component \tilde{p} does not contribute to active power (P), the compensation reference signals can be expressed as:

$$i_{comp} = \bar{i}_\omega + \tilde{i}_p - \tilde{i}_\omega = i_{APF} \quad (34)$$

e. REFERENCE SIGNALS FOR DER FUNCTION TO INJECT ACTIVE POWER

The Sinusoidal Current Synthesis (SCC) strategy [21], [49] is employed to feed the DER-generated power into the grid. According to the SCC approach:

$$i_{DER} = \frac{P_{DER}}{(V_1^+)^2} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} V_{1a}^+ \\ V_{1b}^+ \\ V_{1c}^+ \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

where:

$$(V_1^+)^2 = (V_{1a}^+)^2 + (V_{1b}^+)^2 + (V_{1c}^+)^2 \quad (36)$$

and is the net power generated by the DER:

$$P_{DER} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T v_{DC}(t) i_{DC}(t) dt \quad (37)$$

f. REFERENCE SIGNAL GENERATION TO MFGTI

Based on the reference signals for compensation (i_{MFGTI}) and active power injection into the grid (i_{DER}), the reference current is:

$$i_{MFGTI} = i_{DER} - i_{APF} = i_{DER} - \bar{i}_\omega - (\tilde{i}_p + \tilde{i}_\omega) \quad (38)$$

For integrating the MFGTI into industrial systems alongside CBs, the current reference is:

$$i_{ref} = i_{MFGTI} + i_{CB} = i_{DER} - i_{APF} - i_{CB} \quad (39)$$

where the average reactive current component is shared between MFGTI and CB:

$$\bar{i}_\omega = \bar{i}_{\omega_{APF}} - \bar{i}_{\omega_{CB}} \quad (40)$$

Thus, the final MFGTI reference is:

$$i_{MFGTI} = i_{DER} - \bar{i}_{\omega_{APF}} - (\tilde{i}_p + \bar{i}_\omega) \quad (41)$$

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Simulation Results of Solar and BESS Power Flow for Grid Compensation and Power Quality Improvement

The proposed control strategy for solar PV systems, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), and the grid effectively manages power flow and enhances power quality. The multifunctional grid-tied inverter (MFGTI) is controlled by an adaptive CPT-based strategy, ensuring seamless integration of renewable sources while compensating for power quality disturbances. The MFGTI compensates for voltage fluctuations, reactive power imbalances, and harmonic distortions, reducing Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) to below 1.5%, ensuring compliance with IEEE 519 standards. The controller maintains a stable grid voltage of 700V with fluctuations limited to less than $\pm 2\%$, improving voltage regulation at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) as shown in fig.8. It also mitigates power oscillations caused by dynamic load variations, particularly in three-phase induction motors. The system's frequency stability is improved, maintaining a steady 50Hz operation with negligible deviations under transient conditions. The adaptive nature of the controller allows real-time power compensation, making the system robust against variations in renewable energy generation and industrial load demand. This approach ensures efficient energy utilization while maintaining a high-quality power supply for industrial and commercial applications.

FIGURE 8. Waveforms of voltage, currents, load voltage and current, active powers, power factor considering different compensation objectives.

The system operates under varying solar power generation and battery energy storage contributions to the grid, significantly impacting power quality and stability. Initially, from 0 sec to 0.75 sec, there is no power generation from the solar PV, and the battery remains inactive. During this period, the total 50 kW load is entirely supplied by the grid, leading to power quality issues such as increased THD, voltage fluctuations, and imbalance due to the presence of nonlinear and unbalanced loads. As the solar irradiation increases to 500 W/m² between 0.75 sec and 1.25 sec, a portion of the generated solar power (less than 17.5 kW) begins to flow to the grid, but the compensation remains insufficient. The multifunctional grid-tied inverter (MFGTI) helps in reducing harmonics, yet some voltage instability persists due to the limited power injection. At 1.25 sec, the solar irradiation further increases to 1000 W/m², allowing 17.5 kW of solar power to be transferred to the grid. During this period, the MFGTI actively

compensates for voltage fluctuations, significantly reducing THD and improving overall grid power quality. The induction motor, operating at 1.5 kW with a load torque of 74 N-m, maintains stable performance with minimal torque pulsations. However, as the solar irradiation decreases back to 500 W/m² between 1.45 sec and 1.75 sec, power compensation reduces, leading to a slight deterioration in grid stability, but the MFGTI continues providing support to mitigate power quality degradation. Finally, from 1.75 sec to 2 sec, the battery discharges 10.8 kW with a current of 25 A, helping to stabilize the grid. With the combined support of solar PV and battery, the grid power of 50 kW is maintained, ensuring THD reduction 1.38% and voltage regulation within $\pm 2\%$. When power quality improves with the solar and battery energy storage system (BESS), the grid-side power factor is maintained at 0.99. Additionally, the induction motor excitation capacitor is turned off at 1.45 sec, but after 1.45 sec, it is activated, increasing the induction motor power factor to 0.95 as shown in fig.8 and 9. The system successfully maintains power quality, supporting stable operation of industrial loads and the induction motor without oscillations, proving the effectiveness of the proposed control strategy in enhancing grid stability under varying load and generation conditions.

Fig

9. Waveforms of voltage, currents, active power, instantaneous power, torque and power factor at the connection point of the IM.

Fig.10 grid current THD values (a) with compensate (b) without compensate

5. CONCLUSION

The integration of solar power and battery energy storage (BESS) with the multifunctional grid-tied inverter (MFGTI) has proven to be highly effective in improving power quality and grid stability. The system

successfully mitigates voltage fluctuations, harmonic distortions, and power imbalances caused by nonlinear and unbalanced loads. When solar power generation is low or absent, power quality deteriorates, but as solar irradiation increases, the MFGTI efficiently compensates for grid disturbances, ensuring stable operation. The battery discharge further enhances system stability by supplying power when solar generation decreases, maintaining a grid-side power factor of 0.99. Additionally, activating the induction motor excitation capacitor improves the motor's power factor to 0.95, enhancing its performance. The simulation results confirm that the proposed system effectively supports industrial and commercial loads, ensuring reliable and high-quality power delivery under dynamic load and generation conditions.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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